

Block 1

Adaptive user interface for mHealth applications-Discrete choice experiment survey

Thank you for interest in our survey!

We are inviting you to participate in a study exploring how different factors will affect user's preference for different designs of adaptation in the mHealth applications. This study explores the relative importance of several aspects that affect mHealth with adaptive user interface adoption, specifically for people with chronic diseases. Your responses to this survey are strictly confidential and at no time will your answers be linked to your identity. This survey will take approximately 13 minutes to complete.

For the best experience, we recommend completing the survey on a **desktop device**.

For more information, please read the explanatory statement for this project. If you have any questions, please email wei.wang5@monash.edu. Ethical approval has been provided by Monash University. Further details can be provided upon request.

After completing the informed consent form, there are three parts to this survey:

Section A: Your demographic information.

Section B: Discrete choice experiment for adaptive user interfaces.

Section C: Your health status.

Survey Consent Form

- I have read and understood the Explanatory Statement and I hereby consent to answer the online survey
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.
- I agree that the data I provide in this research may be used by the investigators in future research projects.

Enter your PROLIFIC ID (Please note that this response should auto-fill with the correct ID)

`#{e://Field/PROLIFIC_PID}`

Section A: About you(1/2)

Section A: About you (1/2)

NOTE: We assure you that all shared details and all other confidential information will be kept confidential. Your name and details will not be identified in any publication or report.

Has a health care provider ever told you have a chronic disease ?

I have chronic diseases (You may provide additional details about your health below)

No I do not have chronic diseases

Other (Please specify)

Have you used mHealth apps before to manage your chronic disease or prevent chronic conditions?

The most common application of mHealth is the use of mobile devices to educate consumers about preventive healthcare services. However, mHealth is also used for disease surveillance, treatment support, epidemic outbreak tracking and chronic disease management.

Yes, I have used/curently use the mHealth application (You may provide additional details about the app below)

No, I never used before

Other (Please specify)

Section A: about you

Section A: About you (2/2)

NOTE: We assure you that all shared details and all other confidential information will be kept confidential. Your name and details will not be identified in any publication or report.

In what age group are you?

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 - 84
- 85 or older

To which gender identity do you most identify as?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / third gender
- Prefer not to say
- Other (Please specify)

In which country do you currently reside?

Which one of these groups would you say best represents your race?

- White
- Black or African American
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander
- Multicultural
- Other (Please specify)

What is your highest educational qualification?

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Section B: Discrete choice experiment for adaptive user interfaces (1/2)

mHealth (Mobile Health)

mHealth, or mobile health, refers to the use of mobile devices—like smartphones, tablets, and wearable devices—to support health-related activities. These can range from apps that monitor physical activity or nutrition to those that track chronic health conditions, manage medications, or offer remote consultation options.

Adaptive User Interfaces

An adaptive user interface is a user interface which adapts its layout and elements to the needs of the user or context. Adaptive user interfaces can enhance mHealth applications by making them more responsive to the unique needs of users.

Here are two examples of adaptive user interfaces:

1. Exercise application: The left side is a standard version of the interface, to maintain usability and readability of the interface when the user is running, the interface automatically hide images and

changes small-font and enlarge the subtitle and two buttons.

2. PD-Helper for Parkinson's Disease Patients: Users are allowed to change the font size and other settings in accordance with their own preferences and capabilities

1. Exercise application

2. PD-Helper for Parkinson's Disease Patients

Background information for questionnaire

Section B: Discrete choice experiment for adaptive user interfaces (2/2)

In this section, we are exploring your preferences for **different adaptation design** in mobile health (mHealth) applications, specifically those that support chronic disease management.

About the Choice Task

You will be presented with a series of choice sets (see the **example choice set** below), each showing **two** hypothetical options for an adaptive mHealth application. Each choice set presents different combinations of key factors that influence how the app could adapt to meet user needs. You might see some statements repeated across different sets, but each question is unique in its specific combination of options.

	Option 1	Option 2
Involvement of caregivers	Active involvement and jointly utilise the app.	No access.
Usability of the app	Unpredictable and requiring users to learn it due to adaptations.	The app is easy to use and understand, with a familiar interface that makes navigation straightforward.
Controllability over adaptations	Limited user options to control how the app adapts.	Easy to use with a familiar interface.
Frequency of adaptations	Adapt (only) once when user logs in.	Adapt monthly.

Granularity of adaptations	Adaptations are broad and impact the app significantly.	Adaptations are specific, affecting small aspects of the app.
Function usage patterns	Several times a day	Less than once a week
	○	○

What We're Looking for in Your Choices (Key factors)

For each choice set, please select the adaptation design option that best aligns with your preferences. You can review the details of the factors by clicking on [this link](#) or by referring to the key factors listed below:

- **Involvement of caregivers:** This describes the role of caregivers in your daily use of the mHealth applications.
- **Usability of the App:** This refers to how easy or intuitive the app is to use, even with the different adaptations.
- **Controllability Over Adaptations:** This factor considers how much control you, as the user, have over the way the app adapts to your needs.
- **Frequency of Adaptations:** This shows how often the app's features change to match your preferences, which could range from occasional updates to more frequent adjustments
- **Granularity of Adaptations:** This highlights the scale of changes, whether they're broad adjustments affecting many parts of the app or small, targeted changes.
- **Function Usage Patterns:** This aspect reflects the app's adaptability based on how frequently you use different functions.

Comprehension check and attention check

Please review the [key factors](#) thoroughly before answering the following questions and **ensure the key factors file are open** in another window for reference. We have included comprehension check questions in the survey to ensure that all participants are familiar with the key factors provided. If you are uncertain about an answer, we encourage you to revisit the key factors. Additionally, since this survey does not include open-ended questions, we have included attention check questions to ensure accurate and thoughtful responses.

Based on the **key factors** you have reviewed, can you identify which two factors are addressed in the statement below?

"I record my blood pressure every day using the app, and I prefer not to see changes in the user interface each time I log in."

If you're unsure of the answer, please take a moment to reread the key factor before responding.

- Frequency of adaptations
- Function usage patterns
- Usability of the app
- Involvement of caregivers
- Controllability over adaptations
- Granularity of adaptations

Completing the Task

In the following section, you will go through **10** different choice sets. Each set requires you to review two options carefully and choose the one that best aligns with your preferences. We have randomized the choice sets, so ***you cannot go back to this information page when you click next on this page.***

Please click **>>Next** only when you have opened the **key factors** file in another window for your reference.

ConjointBlock (1-10)

In general, would you say your health is?

- Very Poor
- Poor
- Fair
- Good
- Very Good

What type of long-term medical conditions you currently have? (Select as many as apply to you)

- Cardiometabolic (e.g., diabetes, high blood pressure, obesity, and heart disease)
- Respiratory (e.g. allergies, asthma, and chronic lung disease)
- Immune-related (e.g., cancer, Parkinson's disease, and compromised immune system)
- Others, Please specify

How do you usually manage stress caused by various health issues?

- I ignore or avoid dealing with the stress.
- I sometimes avoid it but try to stay positive.
- I manage it with a mix of positive thinking and avoidance.
- I mostly stay positive and try to handle it effectively.
- I actively manage the stress and stay positive throughout.

How do you usually manage other types of stress base on the instruction below?

This is an attention check, please select "I manage it with a mix of positive thinking and avoidance" for this question.

- I ignore or avoid dealing with the stress.
- I sometimes avoid it but try to stay positive.
- I manage it with a mix of positive thinking and avoidance.
- I mostly stay positive and try to handle it effectively.
- I actively manage the stress and stay positive throughout.

How often do you use mHealth technology ?

The most common application of mHealth is the use of mobile devices to educate consumers about preventive healthcare services. However, mHealth is also used for disease surveillance, treatment support, epidemic outbreak tracking and chronic disease management.

- Less than once a month
- Once a month
- Several times a month
- Once a week
- Several times a week
- Daily
- Others, Please specify

Do you have any further suggestions for this research?

Do you want to receive future updates from our study?

Yes (Leave your email)

No

Other

Study name: "Evaluating adaptive user interfaces for chronic disease applications"
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Monash University values the privacy of every individual's personal information and is committed to the protection of that information from unauthorised use and disclosure except where permitted by law. For information about the handling of your personal information please see the applicable [Statement](#) which applies to you in the context of this survey.

For more information about Data Protection and Privacy at Monash University please see our [Data Protection and Privacy Procedure](#).

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